

28th International ICFMH Conference

Organized by:

International Committee
on Food Microbiology
and Hygiene

Under the auspices:

UNIVERSIDAD
DE BURGOS

TECHNOLOGICAL EVOLUTION
AND REVOLUTION IN FOOD
MICROBIOLOGY

foodmicro2024.com

July, 8-11, 2024
Fórum Evolución
Conference Centre
and Auditorium
Burgos (Spain)

FINAL PROGRAM

Table of contents

Welcome address	4
About ICFMH	7
Committees	8
General Information	10
Venue Halls and Levels	14
Acknowledgments	15
Exhibition Floor Plan	16
Scientific Program	
Program Overview	19
Scientific Program	21
Posters	53

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Welcome address

Dear colleagues,

It is a great pleasure to welcome you all to our city of Burgos in Spain to attend the 28th ICFMH International Conference, FoodMicro 2024. Since the International Conferences began in the last century, this is the first time it has been held in Spain. We want to express our gratitude to the executive committee of the ICFMH for choosing the city Burgos for this occasion.

Burgos is a nice city located 220 km north of Madrid, in the midway to the Atlantic seashore in Santander in northern Spain. An area that traditionally has been inhabited from more than 1 million years. Here, in the surroundings of the city, in the archeological site of Atapuerca, the remains of the so called the first European have been discovered, dating back more than 1.2 million years. The climate of this area has done the rest and in Atapuerca human fossils from most of the human phylogeny of Europe have been found, bones that you can see in the Museum of Human Evolution, which is located in the center of the city, next to the Congress Venue Fórum Evolución. Hence, Burgos is the European city of Human Evolution.

Here, in Burgos is where we developed our scientific career and research in food microbiology over the last 30 years in the Department of Biotechnology and Food Science of the University of Burgos, which was also born 30 years ago. Therefore, we think it will be a nice celebration for our university to welcome everyone to Burgos to attend FoodMicro 2024. During that time, there has also been a great evolution in food microbiology research in preparation of the big revolution that is now being produced involving new and powerful methodologies based on omics and other techniques. All this gives us a new insight of classical topics as food fermentations, probiotics or protective cultures, new technological interventions to extend the shelf-life and to improve food safety, new topics related to food environments such as primary production, food producing plants and its interaction with food products, the microbiome, etc.

For this reason, Burgos is the right place to talk and debate about this technological evolution and revolution in Food Microbiology. It is the place where everything begins with our ancient parents fighting to survive in a hard environment to evolve to the

present day. A city in the middle of Saint James' Way, where the knowledge exchange 800 years ago, brought through this way made possible the construction of the magnificent Gothic cathedral that stands in the middle of the city, which you will observe while discussing food microbiology in the Congress Venue.

Dear colleague, don't miss this opportunity to exchange ideas and do networking with other colleagues in the 28th International Conference of ICFMH. We have prepared an excellent program to facilitate this purpose including for the first time in FoodMicro Conference: Flash Communications to give more opportunities to young researchers to explain their research to the audience; Round Tables to give the audience a different way to discuss the research ideas behind the topics proposed and a congress party in the gardens of the university where you could enjoy, meet each other better and explore synergies for future research collaborations.

Welcome all of you to Spain and Burgos, enjoy our city, our culture and gastronomy and the good wines elaborated in this area.

Ah and don't forget your sunglasses!

Jordi Rovira (President), Beatriz Melero, Isabel Jaime
University of Burgos
Local Organizing Committee

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Dear Colleagues and Friends,

It is my great pleasure to welcome you to the upcoming International Committee on Food Microbiology and Hygiene (ICFMH) congress in Burgos, Spain. This year, our focus is on the latest advances in new technologies in food production and microbiological analysis, and we are thrilled to bring together experts, researchers, regulators, and industry professionals from around the world to share knowledge and exchange ideas.

Revolutionary advancements in technology are transforming the field of food microbiology and hygiene, leading to unprecedented opportunities for scientific evolution. The congress will offer an exciting opportunity to delve into cutting-edge research and technological breakthroughs, exploring the ways in which innovation is driving improvements in food safety and quality. This will surely cover all aspects from the wet lab studies to in silico work as well as global changes that influence food web.

Keynote speakers and scientific sessions will cover a range of topics, including new trends in food processing, innovative approaches to food safety and quality, and novel methods for microbial analysis. We will also for the first time tackle some emerging fields such as microplastics and microbiome interactions. By sharing insights and exploring new ideas together, we hope to spark new collaborations and inspire future innovation in the field.

Beyond the scientific program, we have organized social events that will give you the opportunity to immerse yourself in the rich history and culture of Burgos, Spain. We are confident that this congress will offer an unforgettable experience for all attendees, fostering new collaborations, sharing insights, and providing opportunities to expand your knowledge.

We look forward to welcoming you to the ICFMH congress in Burgos, Spain, where we will explore the ways in which the revolution in technology is driving scientific evolution in the field of food microbiology and hygiene.

Sincerely,

Prof. Dr. Andreja Rajkovic

President, International Committee on Food
Microbiology and Hygiene (ICFMH)

About “ICFMH”

The International Committee on Food Microbiology and Hygiene was founded in 1953. The major scope of ICFMH is to contribute to food safety and controlling food spoilage internationally, by means of organizing conferences (e.g. FOODMICRO), symposia and workshops, supporting of international bodies in food microbiology issues, publications (e.g. the International Journal of Food Microbiology), and initiation of education and training in food microbiology.

The ICFMH particularly focuses on the food safety situation in developing countries, with a special mission towards the African situation.

www.foodmicro2024.com

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Technical Secretariat

Amex GBT Meetings & Events

AMEX GBT

Meetings
& Events

General Information:

foodmicro2024@amexgbt.com

Registrations:

registrationfoodmicro2024@amexgbt.com

Abstracts:

abstractsfoodmicro2024@amexgbt.com

Let's get social

@FoodMicroconference

[instagram.com/foodmicro2024](https://www.instagram.com/foodmicro2024)

@foodmicro2024

Official hashtags: #foodmicro2024

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Committees

Honor Committee

Excmo. Sr. D. Alfonso Fernández Mañueco. Presidente de la Junta de Castilla y León
Excma. Sra. D.ª Rocío Lucas Nava. Consejera de Educación de la Junta de Castilla y León
Excmo. Sr. D. Manuel Pérez Mateos. Rector Magnífico de la Universidad de Burgos

Honorary Presidents

Mogens Jacobsen. University of Copenhagen, Denmark
Wilhelm Holzapfel. Handong Global University, Korea

Local Organizing Committee

University of Burgos, Spain

Jordi Rovira (President)

Beatriz Melero

Isabel Jaime

Social media manager

David Sáez

International Committee on Food Microbiology and Hygiene

Andreja Rajkovic. Ghent University, Belgium

Wei huan Fang. Zhejiang University, China

Sara Bover i Cid. Institute for Food Research and Technology, Spain

Vasilis Valdramidis. National and Kapodistrian University of Athens, Greece

Luca Cocolin. University of Turin, Italy

Bernadette Franco. University of São Paulo, Brazil

Jesca Nakavuma. Makerere University, Uganda

Peter Raspor. University of Primorska, Slovenia

Tom Ross. University of Tasmania, Australia

National Scientific & Organizing Committee

Beatriz Melero. Chairperson,
University of Burgos

Ana Allende. CEBAS., Murcia

Avelino Álvarez. University of León

José Antonio Beltrán. University of
Zaragoza

Juana Frías. Institute of Food Science,
Technology and Nutrition (ICTAN, CSIC)

Antonio Gálvez. University of Jaén

Rosa M. García. University of Córdoba

Rafael Pagán. University of Zaragoza

Miguel Prieto. University of León

David Rodríguez. University of Burgos

Susana Sanz. University of La Rioja

Carole Tonello. Hiperbaric

Antonio Valero. University of Córdoba

International Scientific Committee

Mirjana Andjelkovic. Sciensano, Belgium

Johanna Björkroth. University
of Helsinki, Finland

Luca Cocolin. University of Turin, Italy

Franchesca de Filippis. University
of Naples Federico II, Italy

Heidy den Besten. Food Microbiology
Wageningen University, The Netherlands

Frank Devlieghere. Ghent University,
Belgium

Danilo Ercolini. University of Naples
Federico II, Italy

Pieter Gouws. Stellenbosch University,
South Africa

Sophia Johler. University of Zurich,
Switzerland

Anja Klancnik. University of Ljubljana,
Slovenia

María Lara. Yale University, USA

Marta Laranjo. University of Évora,
Portugal

Julius Maina Mathara. Jomo Kenyatta
University of Agriculture and Technology,
Kenia

Paola Mattarelli. University of Bologna,
Italy

Maarten Nauta. Statens Serum Institut,
Denmark

Ilenys Perez-Diaz. USDA. Agricultural
Research Service, USA

Andreja Rajkovic. Ghent University,
Belgium

Kalliopi Rantsiou. University of Turin, Italy

Panagiotis Skandamis. Agricultural
University of Athens, Greece

Paula Teixeira. Catholic University of
Portugal (UCP)

Olakunle David Teniola. Olusegun
Agagu University of Science and
Technology (OAUSTECH), Nigeria

Martin Wagner. University of Veterinary
Medicine Vienna, Austria

Marcel Zwietering. Food Microbiology
Wageningen University, The Netherlands

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General Information A-Z

A

ACCOMMODATION

ABBA BURGOS 4*

C. Fernán González, 72 [1 km]

CORONA DE CASTILLA 4*

C. Madrid, 15 [550 m]

RICE PALACIO DE LOS BLASONES 4*

C. Fernán González, 72 [650 m]

SILKEN GRAN TEATRO 4*

Av. del Arlanzón, 8 [240 m]

HOTEL NORTE Y LONDRES 2*

Pl. de Alonso-Martínez, 10 [550 m]

Residencia Univ. "CAMINO DE SANTIAGO"

C. José M^a Villacián Rebolledo, s/n [2,5 km]

B

BURGOS

Burgos is a modern city, which is immersed in a profound process of urban, tourism and cultural transformation. The recent creation of large infrastructures, including the Human Evolution Complex, represents a decisive change in the appearance of the city. Burgos, which

has made a firm commitment to tourism and culture over the last decade, aspires to become a benchmark for conference and incentive tourism.

Burgos has some tourist attractions that are unique in the national panorama. It has an artistic heritage with three declared World Heritage Cultural Sites: The Cathedral, the Camino de Santiago and the Archaeological Site of Atapuerca.

Tourism information office

Calle Nuño Rasura, 7, Burgos
+34 947 288 874

Link: turismo.aytoburgos.es/en | turismoburgos.org | spain.info/en/destination/burgos

Bus Station: C/ Miranda 4-6,
09002 Burgos | +34 947 288 855

Rosa Manzano Train Station:
Avenida Príncipe de Asturias s/n,
09006 Burgos | +34 902 320 320

Taxi Services Abu taxis / Radio taxi
+34 947 277 777

C

COFFEE

- Located on the 1st floor of the Fórum Evolución.
- It has direct access from the street, through its terrace, and has incredible views of the Burgos cathedral and the city center.

CERTIFICATES OF ATTENDANCE

Certificates of Attendance will be delivered by email to delegates that have attended the scientific program, after completion of the Foodmicro 2024.

CLOAKROOM

A cloakroom will be available during the congress. It will be located next to the main entrance.

- Monday July 8th from 16:00 to 21:30
- Tuesday July 9th and Wednesday July 10th from 08:30 to 19:00
- Thursday July 11th from 08:30 to 14:30

E

EMERGENCY CONTACT

Emergency contact number: 112

EXHIBITION OPERATING

All exhibitors are listed in the Program (see Exhibition floor plan).

The exhibition will run during the Conference dates at ground floor lobby as follows:

- Tuesday July 9th and Wednesday July 10th from 08:30 to 19:00
- Thursday July 11th from 08:30 to 14:00

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F

FOOD & BEVERAGES

Coffee and Lunch during official breaks are included in the delegate registration fee and will be served in designated catering stations in all Conference areas.

- Coffee. Exhibition and Poster Area. Ground floor lobby and 3rd floor hall
- Lunch. 3rd floor hall

I

INSURANCE & LIABILITY

- The registration fees do not include insurance of participants against accidents, sickness, cancellation, theft, property loss or damage. Participants are advised to take out adequate personal insurance.
- Registration implies acceptance of the congress rules and its conditions of participation and cancellation.
- The Organizers of the 28th International ICFMH Conference reserve the right to limit the capacity of the in-person Conference due to the need to ensure the health and safety of attendees, in accordance with the recommendations of the World Health Organization, Health (WHO) and local Health Authorities, at the time of the Conference.

INTERNET

- **WiFi network:** foodmicro2024
- **Password:** burgos2024

L

LOST & FOUND

A lost and found service is available at the Cloakroom.

P

PARKING

- The **Human Evolution Parking** is a municipal facility, which has more than **1,400 spaces** and it is located under the conference venue.
- It is a **modern space**, with excellent facilities and **affordable rates**.
- The entrance to the Parking is located on C/ Burgense. Price: 12.60 € /24 h.

Telephone: + 34 947 25 51 24

R

REGISTRATION DESK

The Registration Desk and Onsite Secretariat is in the ground floor lobby level (0) of the Conference Venue and will be operating throughout Conference dates according to the following schedule:

- Monday, July 8th: 16:00 to 20:00
- Tuesday, July 9th: 08:30 to 19:00
- Wednesday, July 10th: 08:30 to 19:00
- Thursday, July 11th: 08:30 to 14:00

Important note: Your badge is your personal identification to enter the Conference. Due to attendance limitations and protocols, entry to Conference areas will be monitored, so please be mindful of your badge for the Conference. **In case of loss**, an administrative fee of 20 € will be charged for reprinting.

New accreditations can be processed starting at 16:00 on Monday, July 8th at the Registration Desk.

S

SOCIAL PROGRAM

Get together

Monday, July 8th | 19:30 to 21:30 | Ground floor lobby Fórum Evolución

Party

Wednesday, July 10th | 20:30 to 23:00

Gardens of University of Burgos (Hospital del Rey) "Facultad de Derecho y Rectorado de la Universidad de Burgos", Hospital del Rey, s/n; Burgos.

Distance from the conference site: 38 min. within walking distance | By car: 6 min | Bus Lines: 3, 5.

Dresscode: Casual

Ticket: Free, the dinner is included in your

registration fee. Advance confirmation of attendance is required.

The Foodmicro Organizers will be throwing an afterwork party (cocktail type) where you will be able to taste some typical Spanish tapas, enjoy music and get together with colleagues from all over the world.

V

VENUE

Universidad de Burgos: Preconference Workshops. Facultad de Derecho

Hospital del Rey, s/n. 09001 Burgos
+34 947 258 701

Fórum Evolución Burgos.

Palacio de Congresos y Auditorio

Paseo Sierra de Atapuerca s/n. Burgos
+34 947 25 95 75

W

WEATHER

The weather in the province of Burgos has a marked continental character, with long and cold winters, short and not excessively hot summers. Usual July temperature:

Maximum temperatures range from 25 to 27 °C and rarely drop below 19 °C or exceed 33°C.

Daily minimum temperatures range from 11 to 12 °C and rarely fall below 7 °C or exceed 15 °C.

Halls and Levels

GROUND FLOOR

- 01 Auditorium
- 02 Exhibition + Poster Area + Coffee
- 03 Cloakroom
- 04 Lifts
- 05 Loading presentation area + Speaker room
- 06 Registration desk + Technical secretariat
- 07 Rest area

3^{ST.} FLOOR

- 01 Lunch
- 02 Meeting Room B
- 03 Meeting Room A
- 04 Lifts
- 05 Poster Area + Coffee

4^{ST.} FLOOR

- 01 Executive Committee Room
- 02 Lifts

Acknowledgments

Institutional Partners

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Exhibition Floor Plan

BOOTHS

 avantor™

2

 BRUKER

5

ELSEVIER

6

 foods
an Open Access Journal by MDPI

 pathogens
an Open Access Journal by MDPI

11

 GSC

3

 International Association for
Food Protection®

4

ThermoFisher
SCIENTIFIC

10

**SCIENTIFIC
PROGRAM**

Monday, July 8th

University of Burgos PRE-CONFERENCE WORKSHOPS

09:00-11:00	AULA ROMEROS WORKSHOP 1 Microplastics and microbiome interactions: Sharing insights and exploring new pathways	AULA ALFONSO VIII WORKSHOP 2 Nonthermal technologies for food preservation: Current applications and future trends
11:00-11:30	Coffee break	
10:00-13:00	AULA RUTÁ JACOBEA WORKSHOP 3 FoodSafeR: A joined-up approach to protect european food from biological and chemical hazards	
11:30-13:30	AULA ROMEROS WORKSHOP 4 Microbial food safety workshop for developing countries: Opportunities for mitigation of foodborne pathogens by natural preservatives	
Fórum Evolución Burgos, Conference Center and Auditorium AUDITORIUM		
11:00-11:30	Opening Ceremony	
11:30-19:30	Inaugural Plenary Conference: Food microbiology in retrospect and prospect	
19:30-20:00	Musical Opening: Concert by Fetén Fetén	
GROUND FLOOR LOBBY		
20:00-21:30	Get together	

Tuesday, July 9th

Fórum Evolución Burgos, Conference Center and Auditorium AUDITORIUM

09:00-10:00	Plenary Session. Towards more sustainable packaging of food: Impact on microbial safety and shelf life of packaged foods	
10:00-11:00	AUDITORIUM Parallel Session 1 Microbial food ecology: from processing plants to food	MEETING ROOM A Parallel Session 2 Technologies for food preservation and sustainability I
11:00-11:30	Coffee break + Posters + Exhibition	
11:30-13:00	AUDITORIUM Parallel session 1 (continuation) Food microbiota and impact on human microbiom Microbial food ecology: from processing plants to food	MEETING ROOM A Parallel session 2 (continuation) Impact of climate on food safety and spoilage Technologies for food preservation and sustainability I
13:00-15:00	Posters - Lunch	EXECUTIVE COMMITTEE ROOM 13:30-14:30 ICFMH National Delegate Meeting
15:00-16:40	AUDITORIUM Parallel session 3 Fermented foods I	MEETING ROOM B 14:00-14:45 Author work: What to consider when publishing your work. Elsevier
15:00-16:40	AUDITORIUM Parallel session 4 New methods in food microbiology	MEETING ROOM A Parallel session 4 New methods in food microbiology
16:40-17:00	Coffee break + Posters + Exhibition	
17:00-17:45	AUDITORIUM Parallel session 3 (continuation)	MEETING ROOM A Parallel session 4 (continuation)
17:45-19:00	AUDITORIUM Rule of lactic acid bacteria bacteriocins in the improving food safety: from simple additives to powerful multi-tasking metabolites	MEETING ROOM A Pushing the boundaries of knowledge in Food Microbiology through the cataloging and detailed exploration of food metagenomes
17:45-19:00	MEETING ROOM B Software Fair Tools for predictive modelling and quantitative microbial risk assessment	
19:30	Visit to Hiperbaric headquarters	

Wednesday, July 10th

Forum Evolución Burgos, Conference Center and Auditorium
AUDITORIUM

09:00-10:00	Plenary session. Type III secretion systems: bacterial nanomachines for protein delivery	
10:00-11:00	AUDITORIUM Parallel session 5 Fermented foods II/Food mycology	MEETING ROOM A Parallel session 6 Foodborne pathogens I
11:00-11:30	Coffee break + Posters + Exhibition	MEETING ROOM B Detailed demonstrations of tools presented at Round Table 3
11:30-13:00	AUDITORIUM Parallel session 5 (continuation)	MEETING ROOM A Parallel session 6 (continuation)
13:00-14:30	Posters - Lunch	EXECUTIVE COMMITTEE ROOM 13:30-14:30 International Journal of Food Microbiology Editorial Board meeting
14:30-16:30	AUDITORIUM Parallel session 7 Technologies for food preservation and sustainability II	MEETING ROOM A Parallel session 8 Foodborne pathogens II
16:10-16:30	Coffee break + Posters + Exhibition	MEETING ROOM B Detailed demonstrations of tools presented at Round Table 3
16:30-17:35	AUDITORIUM Parallel session 7 (continuation)	MEETING ROOM A Parallel session 8 (continuation)
17:35-19:00	AUDITORIUM Persistent bacteria in food and feed processing environments: which, how, where and why Round table sponsored by EFSA	

Thursday, July 11th

Forum Evolución Burgos, Conference Center and Auditorium
AUDITORIUM

09:00-10:00	Plenary session. Food, antimicrobial resistance and one health	
10:00-11:00	AUDITORIUM Parallel session 9 Predictive microbiology and microbial risk assessment	MEETING ROOM A Parallel session 10 Microbial resistance/One health
11:00-11:30	Coffee break + Posters + Exhibition	
11:30-13:00	AUDITORIUM Parallel session 9 (continuation)	MEETING ROOM A Parallel session 10 (continuation)
13:00-14:00	AUDITORIUM Closure session	

Topics

- Fermented foods
- Food microbiota and impact on human microbiome
- Food mycology
- Foodborne pathogens
- Impact of climate change on food safety and spoilage
- Microbial food ecology: from processing plants to food
- Microbial resistance
- New methods in food microbiology
- One health
- Predictive microbiology and microbial risk assessment
- Technologies for food preservation and sustainability
- Food microbes in plastisphere: microbial ecosystem on microplastics

MONDAY, JULY 8th

Pre-Conference Workshops

Venue: *Hospital del Rey, University of Burgos*

09:00-22:00

WORKSHOP 1

Microplastics and microbiome interactions: sharing insights and exploring new pathways

📍 **Aula Romeros**

Chair: **Andreja Rajkovic**. Ghent University, Belgium

Workshop in organization of ICFMH and Horizon2020 project ImpTox

ImpTox in the army of five: CUSP squad collects and analyzes data to decipher role of microplastics and nanoplastics in food safety and public health

Andreja Rajkovic. Ghent University, Belgium

Can microplastics modulate the virulence of *Listeria monocytogenes*?

Irene Ortega Sanz. Ghent University, Belgium

To swim or not to swim: Probing the influence of micro- and nanoparticles on male reproductive cell viability and how plastics react with *Bacillus cereus cereulide*

Bram Jacobs. Ghent University /Sciensano, Belgium